

Risk and Conflict Management

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

Conflicts and risks creeping up are inevitable, and staying on top of them is a crucial task during the timecrunch.

Benefits

These tools hopefully help you navigate the deep waters of risks and conflicts.

Practical recommendations

The pressure is on, you are trying to pitch the best proposal possible, all the while communicating with two dozen partners trying to keep them in the loop, juggling a limited budget, and trying to involve the practice partners despite their lack of time and shared language. Something is bound to slip up.

But not to worry or despair! As long as you are prepared such issues should be manageable. Here are some tools to help manage the unforeseen and unpredictable.

Early Warning System

A good start is half the trouble, run a [Stinky Fish](#) exercise with your consortium to get the early concerns on the table.

More importantly, it sets the stage for an open and transparent social environment, which is the best (defensive) weapon in your arsenal (check out [The Communities of Practice Playbook](#) for more strategies). To continue and maintain an open environment run a [Partnership Healthcheck](#) every once in a while, and/or facilitate more low-key check-in moments (e.g. Creating Safety or the [Safety Check](#) from FunRetrospectives).

Conflict Management

If you actually run into conflicts there are some reading materials to help you prepare and navigate the (personal) problems and reach a stable outcome. Specifically we recommend reading the [Guideline for Conflict Resolution](#) and [Conflict Styles](#). Additional reading: The Communities of Practice Playbook.

Content Risks

Next to the social risks, there are also content-driven risk. There is often no possibility to do preliminary studies, and you will have to take leaps of faith on certain methodologies. There are good guides out there on [Risk Management in Horizon projects](#), but also the simple [SWOT](#) can be useful. Doing this risk assessment with the consortium through [Risk Brainstorming](#) improves MAA and creates ownership.

The PREMIERE project does not claim ownership of the tools referenced herein; credit belongs to their respective creators.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Transparent communication about agenda's, expectations, and results

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Stinky Fish](#)

[Partnership Healthcheck](#)

[Guideline for Conflict Resolution](#)

[Conflict Styles](#)

[Risk Management in Horizon projects](#)

[SWOT](#)

[Risk Brainstorming](#)

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